

FEATURES OF THINKING DEVELOPMENT IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *This article discusses the socio-psychological features of the communication process, the conditions for the development of communication skills in children, and the importance of the didactic approach in the formation of the personality of preschool children.*

Keywords: *preschool age, child, communication, socio-psychological development, characteristics, speech, thinking, interpersonal relations, communication training, communication etiquette, educational activities, elements of informal communication, behavior, personality formation, mental process of reflecting reality, visually effective form of thinking, speech activity, practical activity, thought process, mental action.*

During preschool age, visual thinking develops, which appeared at an early age. At this age, along with visual and effective thinking, elements of verbal and logical thinking begin to form. The main form of mental activity of preschool children is visual-figurative thinking.

When solving necessary problems, preschool children continue to use visual-effective thinking. Visual thinking is in close connection with practical actions that transform the object cognized by the child. During preschool age, the child's practice expands and, under the influence of this, the needs that encourage the child to formulate and solve more diverse and complex mental problems increase. Visual and effective thinking at this age improves and moves to a higher level; this level is distinguished by the following features:

- actions performed by a child of senior preschool age are more often replaced by executive ones, trial actions are practically absent, which indicates the child's ability to predict his own activities;

- in children of senior preschool age, a visually effective solution to a given problem is preceded by a mental solution to this problem, accompanied by a verbal form.

In the process of solving new mental problems by the child, speech activity is included. The formation of an active and passive vocabulary and grammatical structure of speech in a child at this age contributes to the comprehension of the task itself and the awareness of ways to solve it. Speech activity included in the child's practical activity transforms his thought process, this contributes to the transformation of practical action into mental action that has a more complex structure.

The most important prerequisite for visual-figurative thinking in a child is imitation of an adult, during which the child reproduces, models the actions of an adult and builds an image of them. Play in this vein can also be considered a form of imitation, since it is in play activity that the child is able to imagine one object through another. At this age, it does not matter for a child whether the object is similar to what is needed; for him, a stick can turn into a gun or another object.

The imagery of mental activity in preschool children is characterized by such a feature as syncretism - this is the quality of thinking characteristic of a preschooler, in which he thinks in schemes, fused, undifferentiated situations in accordance with the image that he retains on the basis of perception, without its differentiation and sequential analysis by randomly connecting the most striking parts. At this age, the child does not know how to isolate in the preserved image the essential properties of the object that distinguish this particular image. Syncretism in this case is clearly manifested in the way children perceive unfamiliar content. In a small child, a word evokes a specific image of a single object associated with this word. This image is fused, it has not yet been analyzed, and therefore is used as a whole. The first disintegration of the image is carried out by highlighting not an essential feature of the object, but a feature that has received the most powerful and “businesslike” reinforcement in the child’s experience.

The ability to identify in an object its essential features and details, according to which a particular object can be classified into a specific category, arises only in older preschool age. However, if a child encounters an object previously unknown to him, even a child of senior preschool age with emerging verbal-logical thinking returns again to a random listing of all the external signs that he sees, or the child describes the area of use of this object.

Children can group objects correctly if they know the corresponding generalizing word-term. Of great importance for grouping objects are those properties and connections that a preschooler identifies in his practical experience.

The level of development of generalization in preschool age is directly dependent on:

- knowledge of a word-term that will generalize all items in a given group;
- the variety of objects known to the preschooler included in this general group;
- requirements that adults place on a child.

The logical thinking of a preschooler in any form is distinguished by some common characteristic features: easy formulation in a problem and its solution in place of unfamiliar conditions that are more familiar on the basis of a “feeling of familiarity”, the establishment of simple connections not only between the essential properties of objects, but also between random, external, secondary ones parties. This determines the originality of the thought process of preschoolers.

J. Piaget, in his research, discovered certain psychological phenomena associated with the development of intelligence in children of middle preschool age, which later became known as Piaget’s phenomena. Already in middle preschool age, the child is capable of reasoning, but in this reasoning the phenomenon of egocentric speech, which was described by J. Piaget, is manifested. In his conclusions, a child of middle preschool age, despite the ability to reason, notes illogicality and erroneous judgments about the abstract properties of objects that are associated with measurable characteristics, such as quantity, size, volume, etc. This phenomenon is due to the inability of a preschool child to realize the reversibility of operations, a lack of understanding of the principles of maintaining the quantity of the described substance and the number of objects when their shape changes. They manifest themselves in children’s erroneous judgments about the abstract properties of objects, which are associated with their measurable characteristics and are caused by the inability of preschool children to realize the reversibility of operations, misunderstanding of the principles of conservation of the amount of matter and the number of objects when their shape or relative position changes.

There is a complex and contradictory connection between visual-effective, visual-figurative and verbal forms of thinking, as we have already seen above. On the one hand, the child's external actions with various objects turn into internal ones. Thus, we can conclude that practical actions underlie the mental activity of a preschool child.

But on the other hand, the practical action itself requires taking into account changes in the object in the process of action with objects using representations of the previous states of the object and comparing them with the existing ones. In addition, the structure of an external objective action includes its goal, the future result, which exists only in terms of ideas or concepts. The effectiveness of external action is directly dependent on the preschooler's understanding of the general semantic context and on his own accumulated life experience. Consequently, the implementation of practical actions always implies the presence of a figurative plan and is based on it.

Taking into account the connection between practical and mental activity of N. N. Poddyakov identified a special type of child thinking - child experimentation. Children's experimentation represents the unity of visual-effective and visual-figurative thinking and has the task of identifying properties and connections of objects hidden from observation. The initiative for children's experimentation does not come from an adult; a preschool child himself comes to this activity.

During childhood experimentation, a preschool child receives new information, often unexpected for the preschooler himself. This information, obtained through experimentation, contributes to changing the actions themselves and ideas about the object of experimentation. Transformations of the object, which are carried out by the child in the process of experimentation, lead to the child discovering new properties of the object. These new properties discovered by the child allow him to carry out new transformations of a more complex level. The thinking process involves not only the use of already proven ready-made methods of action, but also the creation of new ones. Experimentation activates the search for new actions and develops the courage and flexibility of children's thinking. Independent experimentation gives the preschooler the opportunity to try different options for action, to overcome the constraint of children's thinking with ready-made schemes. Mental activity develops not only from ignorance to knowledge, but also in the opposite direction - from understandable to incomprehensible, from definite to indefinite. The role of the adult in the process is reduced to the creation of special objects or situations that stimulate the child's cognitive activity and promote children's experimentation.

Thus, the mental activity of a preschooler is a complex interaction and interconnection of visual-effective, visual-figurative and verbal-logical thinking, in which a gradual transition of external actions for solving mental problems into the internal plane takes place.

The development of creative thinking in children of different ages is relevant. But in our article we paid attention to children of senior preschool age, this is due to the sensitivity of this age stage. It is in older preschool age that purposeful developmental work, including work on developing creative thinking in children, is more effective. For the preschool education system that has developed in the modern world, this is most important when preparing a child for school.

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